
PEDAGOGICAL DISCOURSE IN THE TEXTBOOKS OF FIRST GRADERS OF NATIONAL SCHOOLS OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Particular importance is being paid to the development of schoolchildren's speech. Reading small passages, expressive reading, mastering the content, storytelling and written work types: dictation, narrative and essay are used to develop student's oral and written speech in mother tongue classes. In the article, in order to determine the literacy of students in schools, the test dictation, test report and test essay, together with various exercises conducted in the course of the lesson to develop oral and written speech, mature thinking, educational dictations, as well as special lessons - educational statement and essay lessons, are discussed.

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Speech is a type of human activity, the use of thinking based on language tools (words, phrases, sentences). Speech performs the function of communication and message, emotional expression of one's thoughts and influence on others.

A well-developed speech serves as one of the important means of active activity of a person with society. For the student, speech is a tool for successful education at school.

What is speech development? If we take into account the work done by the student and his/her in the language, speech development means active and practical acquisition of the language in all aspects (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech). In the case of a teacher, the development of speech means the use of methods and methods that help students to actively master the pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure and connected speech. That is why the grammar and spelling program is divided into four parts (sounds and letters, word, sentence, connected speech), so the sections of the mother tongue program: "Literacy teaching and speech learning" It is called "stiriş", "Reading and speech development", "Grammar, spelling and speech development".

It is necessary to observe several conditions for speech activity, as well as for the development of students' speech:

1. There must be a requirement for a person's speech to surface. The methodical requirement of developing students' speech is to create a situation where the student expresses his opinion, the desire and need to express something verbally or in writing.

2. Any speech should have content and material. The more complete, rich, and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be. Therefore, the second condition for the development of students' speech is to take care of the material aspect of speech-related exercises, so that the child's speech is meaningful.

3. An idea is understandable only if it is expressed using words, phrases, sentences, and speech expressions that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for successful development of speech is arming speech with language tools. It is necessary to give children language examples and create a good speech environment for them. As a result of hearing the speech and using it in their own experience, children develop a conscious "language perception" on which the educational methodology is based.

The methodical condition of speech development is to create a wide system of speech activity, that is, firstly, to perceive a good speech pattern, and secondly, to create conditions for expressing one's opinion using learned language tools.

The child learns the language in the process of speech activity. This is not enough, because it absorbs the speech superficially. There are several aspects of speech acquisition. These are:

1. Learning the norms of the literary language. The school teaches children to distinguish literary language from simple colloquial language, dialect and slang, introduces artistic, scientific and colloquial variants of literary language.

2. Mastering the important speech skills necessary for every member of our society,

i.e. reading and writing skills. With this, the child learns the characteristics of written speech, its difference from oral-conversational speech.

3. Improving students' speech culture. Language is an important means of communication in human society. based on this social importance of the language, special importance is given to the speech culture of the students in the school. In order to fulfill these tasks, the teacher should conduct planned work with the students. For this, it is important to know what is included in the concept of working on the development of students' speech.

Three directions are clearly distinguished in the development of speech: 1) working on words; 2) working on phrases and sentences; 3) work on connected speech.

Lexicology (together with phraseology and stylistics), morphology, syntax serves as a linguistic base for working on words, phrases and sentences; and connected speech is based on logic, literary studies and linguistics of complex syntactic integrity.

The indicated three directions are carried out in parallel: dictionary work provides material for sentences; Working on words, phrases and sentences prepares for connected speech. In turn, a connected story and an essay serve as a means of vocabulary enrichment.

Developing students' speech has its own methodical tools, its own types of exercises. The most important of these are connected speech exercises.

Consistency in the development of speech is provided by the implementation of four conditions, that is, the consistency of exercises, perspective, variety, and the ability to subordinate different types of exercises to a common goal. Each new exercise is connected with the previous one and prepares the students for the next one, adding something new, subject to the common goal.

At school, the development of students' speech is considered the main task of mother tongue teaching. Speech development is not only the task of mother tongue and reading classes, but also of all subjects in the curriculum (science, mathematics, work, visual arts, singing lessons), as well as activities held outside the classroom.

People use language as a tool to express ideas. They think about their thoughts before expressing them aloud. This is internal speech. Internal speech is unheard and unwritten, "thought" (thought) speech, which is directed to the thinking person. External speech is a speech addressed to others, broadcast using sounds or written with graphic symbols. The physiological nature of internal and external speech is the same; difference - in external speech, the sound is emitted or written down as a result of the movement of speech organs; in internal speech, the movement of speech organs occurs without sound.

Internal speech helps to understand and remember the material, it is the only necessary tool for the development of external speech. Thinking is based on internal speech. Internal speech teaches the student to speak externally, to speak, to speak with a sense of responsibility. Thinking in the process of internal speech is an important tool in the growth of the student's speech and thinking.

In the school, not only the external speech of the students, but also the internal speech

is cultivated. Children learn to read internally and absorb material in internal speech. They solve various tasks by themselves, the main thing is to prepare their oral and written opinions.

According to the method of expressing the thought, the speech is oral and written. Oral speech differs from written speech as follows: oral speech is sound speech, and written speech is graphic speech. Auditory sense plays a major role in oral speech, and visual and gestural sense play a major role in written speech. Both oral speech and written speech serve as a means of communication between people, but oral speech occurs in real life conditions, directly in the process of communication; written speech is used directly, separated from specific circumstances, and without the presence of a person.

Oral speech is often in the form of a dialogue, and written speech is in the form of a monologue. Written speech requires logical consistency, without omitting certain language forms, and without excessive repetition, so written speech is considered more complex and abstract.

A number of clearly defined requirements are followed in the development of students' speech.

1. Students' speech should be meaningful. A story or an essay will be meaningful only if it is built on the basis of well-known facts for students, their observations, life experiences, information obtained from books, pictures, radio broadcasts and television shows. If children are allowed to talk about unknown subjects and events they have not seen without sufficient preparation, the speech will be poor and meaningless.

The method of speech development requires careful preparation of material for a story, an essay, that is, gathering material, discussing it, filling it in, separating the main content, placing it in the necessary consistency. Of course, the age characteristics and interests of students are also taken into account.

2. Let there be logic in the speech. It is required that the students' speech should be logically correct, the idea should be presented coherently and reasonably, the main points should not be left out, and unnecessary repetition and redundancy not related to the topic should not be allowed. The logic of speech is determined by good knowledge of the subject, events, and logical error is the result of not knowing the content of the material, choosing the topic without thinking. These two requirements relate to the content and construction of the speech. There are also requirements for the formation of speech in terms of language.

3. Let the speech be clear. The reader should learn to express his facts, observations, impressions not only in a simple statement in accordance with the truth, but also using the best language tools (words, phrases, sentences) with special images.

4. Let the speech be rich in language tools. In order to clearly express the content, the student's speech should be rich in language tools, he should have the ability to choose and use the necessary synonyms and various structured sentences in any situation. Of course, it is not possible to make high demands on the language skills of elementary school students, but the teacher should always keep in mind to increase their vocabulary in educational

work.

5. Let the speech be understandable. oral speech should be understandable to the listener, and written speech should be understandable to the reader. If the speaker or writer composes his speech taking into account the possibility and interest of the listener or reader, he will understand it without difficulty.

6. Let the speech be expressive. If the speech is expressive, i.e. lively, beautiful, persuasive, the general spirit of the story, arguments, selected words, their emotionality, structured sentences, phrases affect the listener or reader. Intelligibility and expressiveness of the speech requires that it be free from any dialect and redundant words.

7. Speech should be correct. It is of particular importance for the school that the speech conforms to the norms of the literary language. Written speech requires correct structure in terms of grammar, spelling and punctuation, and oral speech in terms of spelling. The choice of words and the logic of the speech are very important for the speech to be correct.

The requirements listed above are interrelated and are comprehensively implemented in the system of school work.

Speech is not only a means of expressing an opinion, but also a tool for its formation. Thought serves as the psychological basis of speech, and the condition for its growth is thought enrichment. Successful development of speech only on the basis of mastering the system of mental activity. Therefore, great importance is attached to the preparation, improvement and development of the material, the selection, placement, and logical processes of the students' speech.

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